

THE ROLE OF SIZING RESIN STRUCTURE ON THE MICROMECHANICS OF SINGLE FILAMENT COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The adhesion of Type A and HS carbon fibres with differing epoxy resin sizing coatings has been studied. The presence of a sizing resin on the commercial fibres reduced the interfacial shear strength of the fibre-matrix bond which developed. For aqueous emulsion based coatings a molecular weight dependence was observed which suggested that compatibility with the matrix controlled the formation of the interface. However, deposition from solution lead to the differing conclusion that chemical interaction with the fibre surface had occurred, requiring chemical coupling to the matrix. Solvent extraction of emulsion deposited sizing resins, particularly at elevated temperatures, may have had the same effect.

Keywords: Carbon fibres, Interfacial shear strength, Sizing resins.

1. INTRODUCTION

While the improvements in interfacial shear strength of carbon fibre composites which can be achieved from surface oxidation of the fibres has been studied in detail, the effect of resin size structure has received only limited attention. In recent times, the concept of an interphase region between fibre and matrix as a result of preferential hardener adsorption in epoxy resin composites has also been postulated (1). It has traditionally been assumed that an epoxy sizing resin would dissolve into the matrix and have little effect on the micromechanics of the composites. However, Denison et al (2) showed that diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol 'A' was strongly adsorbed onto carbon fibre surfaces from toluene solution at temperatures lower than that used to cure the matrix of a composite.

The presence of an interphase region may explain the differing performances of glass fibre composites manufactured from alternative fibre supplies (3). Similarly, theoretical studies have indicated that a gradation of properties from fibre to matrix may be beneficial (4).

In this study, the interfacial shear strength of a fibre-matrix combination has been measured in the presence or absence of a sizing resin of differing structure.

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2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Type A carbon fibres were made available from Tenax Fibres GmbH (formerly Akzo) with differing finish: Tenax T-5000 (unoxidised and unsized, AU-U), Tenax J-5001/HTA 7 (standard surface oxidation treatment, unsized, AS-U), Tenax T- 5131 (standard surface oxidation treatment, commercially sized, AS-S) (Table 1). These fibres were used as comparative controls for a more detailed study with Type II or High Strength carbon fibres supplied by RK Carbon Fibres Ltd. These were available as oxidised fibres without sizing resin (HSS-U), with prepreg compatible epoxy resin size (HSS-S) and with a so-called antistatic size (HSS-AS). These were also extracted with Toluene, under reflux at 119°C, and at room temperature, for 1 hour, before drying in vacuo at 50°C. The unsized fibres (HSS-U) were treated with epoxy resin in 1% toluene solution at 119°C: (Ciba Geigy GY 298/, Epikote 828/, and GY 298+80 phr NMA hardener + 40 phr Capcure 3-800, followed by drying at 130°C for 1 hour (HSS-US1,2,3, respectively). The unsized fibres (HSS-U) were also coated with commercial aqueous emulsion sizes (Neoxil 971, 8294, 969) diluted with deionized water, under similar conditions, followed by drying at 130°C. The Neoxil emulsions (DSM Savid Ltd) contain epoxy polymers of differing molecular weight as indicated by the epoxy equivalent weights (EPW) which are Neoxil 971: 3000 ± 500 , Neoxil 8294 : 1500 ± 100 , Neoxil 969 : $300 \pm 30 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$. Fibres coated with these are denoted HSS-UEH, UEM, UEL, respectively in Table 2.

2.2 Interfacial Shear Strength (τ) Measurement

The single-embedded multifragmentation test method was used to measure differences in τ . The data analysis employed the standard Kelly-Tyson analysis. Considering the arguments concerning the general applicability of this analysis, it should be pointed out that the reproducibility of the technique is such that direct comparison of individual values obtained using the same matrix system can yield significant conclusions (5).

The single filaments were extracted from the rovings and adhered to a wire frame which supported the fibre in a PTFE mould in which the resin could be cast. The resin matrix was a flexibilised diglycidylether of Bisphenol A obtained by blending Epikote 828 (Shell plc) (57wt%) with Araldite GY298 (Ciba Geigy plc). The resin was cured with 80 phr nadicmethylenanhydride (NMA) and 40 phr Capcure 3-800 (Henkel-Nopco), a mercaptan terminated polymer. This system was chosen since a cast resin of sufficient failure strain to achieve saturation to the fragmentation process, could be obtained at low curing temperatures. The resin was cured at 55°C for 18 hours followed by post-curing at 130°C.

The strength of the fibres at the critical length l_c , was calculated from the measured Weibull parameters for the strength of the individual fibres. The data used for these calculations is given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: The average strength (σ_1 at $l_f = 5$ mm) and Weibull modulus (m) for the Tenax fibres used in this study

Tenax	Code	σ_1 /GPa	m
T-5000	AU-S	4.42	5.99
T-J 5001	AS-U	3.99	5.74
T-5131	AS-S	3.72	5.10

Table 2: The average strength (σ_1 at $l_f = 6.35$ mm) and Weibull parameters for the differing high strength RK carbon fibres

Code	Sizing	σ_1 /GPa	σ_0 /GPa	m
HSS-U	unsized	4.17	6.96	4.33
HSS-S	epoxy	3.94	6.72	4.5
HSS-AS	antistatic	4.29	6.49	5.46
HSS-US1	GY298	4.5	6.49	6.24
HSS-US2	E828	4.27	6.42	5.56
HSS-US3	GY298/NMA	4.62	7.42	4.78
HSS-UEH	N971	4.23	6.20	6.01
HSS-UEM	N8294	4.16	6.39	5.35
HSS-UEL	N969	4.14	6.29	5.39

σ_0 = Weibull characteristic strength

3. RESULTS

The critical length, l_c , required for the calculation of interfacial shear strength, τ , was obtained from the average fragment length (l) according to the standard equation:

$$l_c = 4l/3 \quad (1)$$

τ was obtained by assuming that the Kelly-Tyson analysis (6) was applicable, which gives the following relationship:

$$\tau = \sigma_{1c} d_f / 2l_c \quad (2)$$

where d_f is the fibre diameter, which was obtained from direct measurement by SEM. σ_{1c} is the strength of the individual filaments at the critical length l_c and was estimated from the Weibull parameters given in Tables 1 and 2, using the following relationship:

$$\sigma_{1c} = \sigma_1 (l_f / l_c)^{1/m} \quad (3)$$

where l_f is the fibre length chosen for the strength measurements. For the Type A and HS fibres $l_f = 5$ mm and 6.35 mm, respectively.

3.1 Type A Fibres

The calculated values of interfacial shear strength (τ) for the as-received fibres in the flexible epoxy resin matrix are given in Fig 1. For each fibre the individual values of τ for differing specimens is given, demonstrating the reproducibility of the testing technique. It is important to stress the reproducibility of the results because of the current discussions regarding the data reduction analysis (7). However, while individual values of τ may not be exact the comparative trends are significant, providing full observation of the fragmentation process has been examined.

As expected, the surface oxidation treatment of the fibres has led to an increase in interfacial bonding as shown by an increase in average value of τ from 18 ± 2 MPa to 33 ± 4 MPa. However, the surprising result was the difference between the values of τ for the unsized fibres (AS-U) and sized fibres (AS-S), in that the latter have a significantly lower value. Since fibre surface treatment of the fibres promotes adhesion to epoxy resins, this result strongly supports the argument that precoating with an epoxy sizing resin creates an apparently weaker interface, because the sizing resin does not dissolve readily into the matrix resin to enable a strong interface to form. Thus an interphase region is formed in which the activity of the fibre to the matrix is reduced. This could arise from strong adsorption of the sizing resin to the fibre surface through the epoxy functionality which would therefore either not be available for coupling with the matrix or hinder the formation of a chemical bond between the matrix and the fibre surface. Both these mechanisms are supported by the XPS study reported elsewhere (2) where the strong adsorption of epoxy resins onto oxidised fibre surfaces was demonstrated. To investigate this effect further, a detailed study of the various sizing treatments is given below.

3.2 High Strength Fibres

3.2.1 As-received Sized Fibres

The results of these studies are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: The interfacial shear strength of commercially sized high strength carbon fibres

Sizing	HSS-U	HSS-S	HSS-AS
	None	Epoxy	Antistatic
l/mm(s.d.)	0.349(0.089)	0.334(0.085)	0.376(0.097)
No of fragments	599	219	434
σ_{1c} /GPa	7.65	7.10	6.83
τ /MPa (s.d.)	53.0 (14.2)	49.5 (13.6)	43.7 (9.6)

s.d. = standard deviation. Estimated for τ from maximum likelihood theory (8).

The trend identified in Fig 1 is also apparent in Table 3, where the epoxy resin sized (so-called prepreg sizing) fibres exhibit a slightly lower value of τ . However, in this case the difference is small and may not be significant. The antistatic sizing resin appears to protect the fibres more effectively as indicated by a higher average fibre strength and larger Weibull modulus (Table 2). However, the interfacial bond which develops is clearly lower (Table 3).

Table 4: The effect of Toluene extraction (at temperature T) on the interfacial shear strength of the epoxy resin composites

Sizing	HSS-U None	HSS-S Epoxy	HSS-S Epoxy	HSS-AS Antistatic	HSS-AS Antistatic
T/°C	22	22	119	22	119
σ_I /GPa	4.43	3.6	3.73	4.0	4.12
l/mm (s.d.)	0.327(0.071)	0.327(0.084)	0.330(0.093)	0.35(0.079)	0.365(0.093)
σ_{Ic} /GPa	6.43	5.12	6.24	6.10	6.37
τ /MPa (s.d.)	46.5 (11.6)	36.5 (5.9)	44.5 (10.6)	41.6 (8.4)	41.7 (8.6)

s.d. = standard deviation. Estimated for τ from maximum likelihood theory (8).

3.2.2 As-received Sized Fibres after Toluene Extraction

Extraction with toluene at room temperature and under reflux had no effect on the subsequent interfacial bond of the HSS-AS fibres. However, the epoxy resin sized fibres exhibited a noticeable change on extraction. The results are summarized in Table 4. With cold toluene, the subsequent value of τ was lower than the as-received control, but on further extraction in refluxing toluene τ increased to value close to that of the unsized fibres after cold toluene extraction. This result could suggest that room temperature extraction had contaminated the surface but the maintenance of τ for HSS-AS fibres tends to disprove this argument, in which case the reduction and subsequent increase in τ with toluene extraction may be important. A change in average molecular weight of the coating may have occurred and this hypothesis is examined in section 3.2.3.

3.2.3 Effect of Molecular Weight of the Epoxy Resin Sizing on τ

Commercial sizing resins in emulsion form were diluted with deionized water for coating onto the unsized fibres. The results of the fragmentation tests are summarized in Fig 2 where the values of τ are compared to that for the unsized fibres. In this case, the strongest interface was achieved with the lowest molecular weight sizing resin. Since the latter will have the highest compatibility with the matrix resin, this tends to suggest that dissolution of the sizing resin into the matrix is the most important mechanism. This result is difficult to correlate with those in Table 4 but extraction with toluene may have modified the surface coating. The trend was reproducible in a differing matrix (9). The reduction in τ for the HSS-S fibres, after extraction with cold toluene is consistent with this since the low molecular weight components of the size are more likely to have dissolved. This aspect is examined further in the next section.

3.2.4 Interfacial Shear Strength of Solution Coated Fibres

The unsized HS fibres were treated with differing epoxy resins from dilute toluene solution. The results of this study are given in Fig 3 where it is seen that there is no significant difference between the two epoxy resins: one is a low molecular weight DGEBA. GY298 is a flexible resin based on a blend of a Bisphenol A based resin with a long chain aliphatic epoxy resin. These were chosen because they are components in the matrix resin. It is assumed that addition of the hardener to the sizing solution would encourage crosslinking of the sizing resin prior to embedding it into the matrix resin.

Figure 1 The interfacial shear strength of as-received Type A fibres in an epoxy resin. AU-U are untreated, unsized; AS-U are surface treated, unsized; AS-S are surface treated, sized.

Figure 2 The interfacial shear strength of HSS carbon fibres in an epoxy resin, after treatment with commercial aqueous emulsion based sizing agents of differing Epoxy Equivalent Weight (EPW). L, M, H refers to low, medium, high molecular weight coating, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

The results presented in Tables 2-4 and Figs 1-3 show that the premise that the sizing resin does not influence the interfacial properties of a carbon fibre composite is incorrect. Generally both the HS and Type A fibres achieved the highest interfacial shear strength, when unsized. The magnitude of τ for the two fibre types differ but this could be attributed to differing fibre manufacturing processes. The lower value of τ for the commercially sized compared to the unsized Type A fibres (Fig 1) strongly suggests that an interphase region forms during fabrication of the composite. A similar trend was observed with the HS fibres but the difference between the sized and unsized fibres may not be as significant (Table 3). However, extraction with a known solvent, cold toluene, had the effect of reducing τ significantly (Table 4). Most likely, this would involve removal of the non-bonded and/or oligomeric soluble resin components present on the fibre surface. The remnant of the sizing appears to inhibit the creation of a strong interface. The inference is that a weak interphasal region may have formed.

Extraction with hot toluene has the effect of increasing τ to a value close to that of the unsized fibre and the original sized fibre. This could have involved either complete removal of the epoxy resin or the promotion of covalent bonding of the sizing epoxy resin to the fibre surface. Experiments with an analogous brominated epoxy resin (9) and the previous surface analysis study (2) strongly suggests that the resin would not be totally removed and a monomolecular remnant must remain on the surface and contribute to the adhesion mechanism. In this case, it is possible that on average only one (of two) epoxy group has reacted leaving the possibility for coupling of the matrix to the fibre surface through the sizing resin.

The observation that extraction of the as-received sized fibres with cold or hot toluene (Table 4) leads to differing values of τ , suggests that the conformation of the epoxy resin on the fibre surface may differ. Furthermore, comparison of Figs 2 and 3 suggests that deposition from solution or from emulsion leads to differing levels of adhesion. The values of τ for fibres which have been solution sized (Fig 3) are comparable to the commercially treated fibres from emulsions which have been extracted with toluene. However, the emulsion sized fibres (Fig 2) exhibit a definite molecular weight dependence which is not evident in Fig 3 for the solution coated fibres. It is important to stress that the epoxy equivalent weight of Epikote 828 ($EPW = 190 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), which is approximately half the number average molecular weight, is less than that of the low-molecular weight size used for fibre UEL ($EPW = 300 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$). Therefore, unless an optimum molecular size exists, we postulate that two mechanisms operate when these fibres are impregnated with resin in the fabrication of a composite. It would appear that epoxy sizing resins deposited from emulsion can be dissolved into the matrix since the molecular weight dependence in Fig 2 follows the expected trend in compatibility with the matrix. However, deposition from solution appears to result in chemical interaction of the sizing resin with the fibre surface. In this case, the interfacial bond in the composite can be determined by the availability of the epoxy groups for copolymerisation with the matrix during cure. Furthermore, any subsequent heat treatment of a conventionally emulsion sized fibre or drying at an elevated temperature may lead to composites with differing interphase structure and interfacial shear strengths.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial shear strengths of a range of Type A and Type HS carbon fibres with differing sizing resins in a flexible epoxy matrix have been measured. For the commercially sized fibres, the unsized ones achieved a higher value of τ than the equivalent sized fibres. The differences between the Type A and HS fibres may indicate differing manufacturing processes. Treatment of the

unsized fibres with epoxy resins from solution or emulsion lead to different values of τ in the same matrix. Comparison with solvent extracted commercially sized fibres suggests that differing interfacial mechanisms may operate. The molecular weight dependence of the emulsion deposited sizing resins suggests that compatibility with the matrix may be most important, whereas deposition from solution or extraction with hot solvent can lead to a strong interaction with the fibre surface. Further research is necessary to confirm these effects but preliminary surface analysis demonstrates that solvent deposition leads to a strongly bound deposit (9).

Figure 3 The interfacial shear strength of HSS carbon fibres in an epoxy resin after sizing with GY298 (US1), E828 (US2) and GY 298/NMA/CAPCURE (US3) from hot toluene.

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